

#HumanMicrobiomeAction

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CHARTING A COURSE FOR MICROBIOME POLICY TOWARDS **ONE HEALTH**

Research on human microbiomes can be puzzling and daunting due to its complexity. However, it holds the potential to transform lives, making it crucial for policymakers and regulatory authorities to take action. The Human Microbiome Action project aims to illuminate the complexities and uncertainties in human microbiome research. By tackling intricate questions in this field, the project seeks to provide a clearer understanding and insights into human microbiomes. This EU-funded project is striving to provide consensus and recommendations about the future of this evolving field across Europe and beyond.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 964590

KNOWN FACTS AND PROJECT BENEFITS

EXPERT COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT:

Human Microbiome Action offers an identifiable community of experts to engage in the regulatory landscape as well as policy elaboration, evolution, evaluation, and implementation.

COLLABORATIVE NETWORKS:

Human Microbiome Action works toward a European Microbiome Centres Consortium (EMCC) and a European Microbiome-Dedicated Surveillance Network. These initiatives will connect key microbiome stakeholders, fostering harmonisation and international discussions on the field's evolution and overseeing microbiome standards and product surveillance.

SEARCH FOR CONSENSUS:

Human Microbiome Action employs robust Delphi surveys to establish consensus on critical microbiome topics, resulting in:

- Clarifying the current state and challenges related to microbiome-based biomarker qualification.
- Harmonising outcomes, metadata and sample processing in microbiome clinical studies.
- Defining how preclinical models contribute to understanding disease causes and treatments.
- Assessing the knowledge and perceptions regarding the readiness of microbiome-based information for use in medical practice and microbiome management by consumers.

CHALLENGES AND AREAS OF FOCUS IN HUMAN MICROBIOMES RESEARCH

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COMPLEXITY OF HUMAN MICROBIOMES:

Difficulties in defining healthy human microbiomes pose socio-economic challenges that the Human Microbiome Action project seeks to address.

STANDARDISATION REQUIREMENTS:

The complex nature of microbiome research needs regulatory science efforts to achieve standardisation, improve reproducibility, and ensure data accuracy and consistency. The project aims to address the lack of awareness about existing standards and enhance their accuracy to streamline research practices.

GDPR COMPLIANCE:

Microbiome data is sensitive and requires GDPR* compliance, raising data privacy and security concerns.

**General Data Protection Regulation*

Collaborative multi-stakeholder actions will be essential to drive advancements in microbiome research. The consensus established in the **Human Microbiome Action Delphi surveys** will be consolidated in **white papers** to pave the way for a harmonised future in the governance and regulation of microbiome research.

HUMAN MICROBIOME ACTION

For further information, please visit our website (humanmicrobiomeaction.eu), and follow the [@SciFoodHealth](#) [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#) accounts. Visit our zenodo.org community for all published and upcoming scientific publications or join the Stakeholder's Advisory Board and provide strategic advice from an external point of view.

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